

Photobromination of *m*-Nitrobenzylidene Malonic Ester. Part I.

BY JNANENDRA CHANDRA GHOSH AND KALIPADA BASU.

The photobromination of *m*-nitrobenzylidene malonic ester does not proceed to completion. The reaction is a reversible one, and depending on the intensity of incident light we obtain photo-chemical stationary state.

A reaction which is very similar to the present one is the photobromination of α -phenylcinnamic nitrile. This reaction has been investigated by Plotnikow (*Zeit. wiss. Photographie*, 1919, 19, 1) and more recently by Berthoud who gives only a summary of his results in the *Transactions of the Faraday Society*, February, 1926.

The velocity of bromination of *m*-nitrobenzylidene malonic ester in the dark is practically negligible, in carbon tetrachloride as solvent. The reaction, however, proceeds fairly quickly under strong illumination, the extent of bromination increasing with increase in the intensity of illumination. In this paper the results of a quantitative study of this reaction in solutions of carbon tetrachloride will be described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A pointolite lamp of 1000 C.P. maintained with a current of 6 amperes kept constant by means of a sliding resistance was used as the source of light. A parallel beam was obtained by placing a convex lens at its focal distance from the source. The light before falling on the reaction vessel passed through filter cells (2.5 c.m. thick) containing copper sulphate (16 g. per 100 c.c.) and methyl green solutions whereby light of mean wave-length 486.5 $\mu\mu$ was obtained.

The intensity of the light was measured by means of a Johansen thermopile and low resistance galvanometer calibrated with a Hefner lamp using Gerlach's values. The reaction vessel of plane-parallel glass slides ($1.5 \times 1.5 \times 1.5$ cm.) with a close fitting glass stopper at the top was kept inside a double jacketed copper box with an opening in front. The copper box was maintained at a constant temperature by circulating water from a thermostat by means of a pump. The intensity of illumination was varied by using lenses of different focal lengths.

The ester was prepared in the laboratory by condensation of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and malonic ester (Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 83, 728) and crystallised twice; m.p. 76° . The bromine was frozen out and then distilled. Merck's reagent carbon tetrachloride was further purified in the laboratory.

One c.c. of the reaction mixture was withdrawn from time to time by means of a pipette and titrated with N/500 thiosulphate solution.

Table I represents the results of experiments with a 500 C.P. pointolite lamp, a lens of 15 cm. focal length and a filter of N/15 copper sulphate solution, 2.5 cm. thick. This filter cuts off the infra-red and a large part of the red light.

TABLE I.
Temperature 32° .

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Equilibrium conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Dibromide Bromine \times Ester
0.0067	0.0070	0.0038	230
0.0050	0.0051	0.0030	233
0.0133	0.00715	0.0021	290
0.0100	0.0051	0.0018	270
			Mean 264

Experiments were then carried out with the 1000 C.P. point-o-lite lamp in approximately monochromatic light using copper sulphate and methyl green filters. The mean wave-length of the incident radiation was 488.5μ . Tables II and III represent the results.

TABLE II.

Intensity of light (488.5 $\mu\mu$) 2.5 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Temperature 32°.

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Equilibrium conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Dibromide
			Bromine \times Ester
0.0100	0.00980	0.0048	210
0.0087	0.00855	0.00355	230
0.0050	0.00525	0.00325	210
0.0050	0.00965	0.00655	250
			Mean 235

TABLE III.

Intensity of light (488.5 $\mu\mu$) 6 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Temperature 32°.

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial con. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Equilibrium con. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Dibromide
			Bromine \times Ester
0.010	0.00995	0.00410	344
0.0087	0.00665	0.00300	399
0.0067	0.00830	0.00435	330
0.0133	0.0066	0.00180	314
			Mean 345

Experiments were then carried out to note the effect of temperature on the equilibrium. Table IV gives the results.

TABLE IV.

Intensity of incident light (488·5 $\mu\mu$) 6 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Temperature 25·5°.

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Equilibrium conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Dibromide
			Bromine \times Ester
0·010	0·010	0·00435	298
0·0067	0·00855	0·00475	276
0·0139	0·0067	0·0020	279

Discussion of Results on Photochemical Stationary State.

In the bromination of α -phenyl cinnamic nitrile, Plotnikow found that the equilibrium constant K was given by the empirical relation,

$$K = \frac{I [1 - e^{-\epsilon d(a-x)}]^2 [b-x]}{x}$$

where I = Intensity of incident light,

ϵ = molecular extinction coefficient.

a and b are the initial concentrations of bromine and acceptor,

x = the concentration of dibromide formed.

This equation is far less rational than the following expression developed in his *Lehrbuch* (pp. 251, 253) for similar reactions.

$$K = \frac{I^2 [1 - e^{-\epsilon d(a-x)}]^2 (b-x)}{x}$$

Berthoud on the other hand found that the equilibrium in the above reaction is independent of the intensity of light and the constant is given by the equation,

$$K = \frac{\{k_1[A] + k_2[ABr_2]\} [Br_2]}{[ABr_2]}$$

When $A\text{Br}_2$ is small compared with A , we obtain the expression for the ordinary law of mass action,

$$K = \frac{[A] [\text{Br}_2]}{[A\text{Br}_2]}$$

It will be seen from Tables I, II, III, and IV, that for the photobromination of *m*-nitrobenzylidene malonic ester, the ratio $[A\text{Br}_2]/[A] [\text{Br}_2]$ given in the fourth column is approximately constant. But unlike Berthoud's results on the bromination of the nitrile, the equilibrium constant in this case changes with variation in the intensity of light.

A comparison of Tables II and III brings out the interesting fact that the ratio of the equilibrium constants 235/345 or 0.68 is equal to the square root of the ratio of incident intensities $\sqrt{2.56/6} = .68$. This is an important relation and as will be shown later it furnishes a clue as regards the mechanism of reaction. It was also noticed that when once photochemical equilibrium has been attained under a definite intensity of illumination, the equilibrium is not in the least shifted, if the reacting system is quickly transferred to darkness. It is quite clear, therefore, that both the bromination of *m*-nitrobenzylidene malonic ester and the decomposition of its dibromide can only take place under the stimulus of light.

From Tables III and IV it will be also seen that the equilibrium constant is only slightly affected by changes in temperature. An increase in temperature, however, favours an increase in the concentration of the dibromide—a result which is the reverse of Plotnikow's observation on the nitrile.

Experiments on the Rate of Bromination.

Since the equilibrium is given by $\frac{\text{Dibromide}}{\text{Br} \times \text{Ester}}$, the velocity of bromination should be given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1(a-x)(b-x) - k_2x \text{ where } a \text{ and } b \text{ represent the initial}$$

concentrations of ester and bromine respectively and x the concentration of dibromide formed.

Now when $a=b$

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1(a-x)^2 - k_2x$$

Integration of this equation gives

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \left\{ \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\lambda(2a+\lambda)}} \left[\log \frac{a+\lambda-x+\sqrt{\lambda(2a+\lambda)}}{a+\lambda-x-\sqrt{\lambda(2a+\lambda)}} - \log \frac{a+\lambda+\sqrt{\lambda(2a+\lambda)}}{a+\lambda-\sqrt{\lambda(2a+\lambda)}} \right] \right\}$$

where $\frac{1}{2\lambda} = \frac{k_1}{k_2} = K$.

Putting a' for $a+\lambda+\sqrt{\lambda(2a+\lambda)}$

and b' for $a+\lambda-\sqrt{\lambda(2a+\lambda)}$,

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{1}{a'-b'} \left[\log \frac{b'}{b'-x} - \log \frac{a'}{a'-x} \right]$$

When a is different from b , the expression for k_1 becomes more complicated. Tables V—VII give the results of experiments on the rate of bromination. Intensity of the incident radiation (488.5 $\mu\mu$) was 6 Hefners-at-100 cm. The time is expressed in minutes.

TABLE V.

Conc. of ester—0.010 M.

Bromine—0.00985 M

$$\frac{1}{2\lambda} = 344_s \text{ Temperature } 33^\circ.$$

Time in mins.	N/500 Bromine	k	
9	9.85 c. c.	...	
20	8.75	0.842	
50	7.3	0.745	
80	6.6	0.681	Mean 0.682
125	5.8	0.660	

TABLE VI.

Conc. of ester—0.0067 M		Conc. of bromine—0.00665 M
$\frac{1}{2\lambda} = 344.$		Temperature 32°.
Time in mins.	N/500 Bromine	<i>k</i>
0	6.65 c. c.	...
20	6.1	0.681
55	5.3	0.703
140	4.4	0.640
		Mean 0.675

TABLE VII.

Conc. of ester—0.010 M		Conc. of bromine—0.0103 M
$\frac{1}{2\lambda} = 298.$		Temperature 25.5°.
Time in mins.	N/500 Bromine	<i>k</i>
0	10.3 c. c.	...
25	9.6	0.294
55	8.9	0.294
95	8.1	0.304
135	7.5	0.304
		Mean 0.299

Tables V and VI give the same value of *k*, showing that the velocity of the direct reaction is not appreciably affected by the ester, bromine or dibromide.

Temperature Coefficient of k_1 and k_2 .

Comparison of Tables V and VII shows that the temperature coefficient of k_1 is about 3.5 ($2.3^{10/6.5}$) for 10°C. We can now calculate the temperature coefficient of k_2 . Let *x* be the temperature coefficient of k_2 for 6.5°C (32—25.5°).

Now at 25.5°, the equilibrium constant $K_1 = \frac{k_1}{k_2}$

$$= 280 \text{ (vide Table IV).}$$

K_2 , the equilibrium constant at 32.5°C = 345 (vide Table III).

Again,

$$K_2 = \frac{k_1 \text{ at } 25.5^\circ \times 2.3}{k_2 \text{ at } 25.5^\circ \times x}$$

$$= K_1 \times \frac{2.3}{x}$$

$$\text{or } 345 = \frac{280 \times 2.3}{x}$$

$$\text{or } x = 1.8.$$

Therefore, the temperature coefficient of k_2 for 10°C

$$= 1.8^{10/2.3} = 2.4 \text{—a value less than that for } k_1.$$

Application of Einstein's Law of Photo-chemical Equivalence.

Although this reaction is a reversible one, during the first twenty or 25 minutes the effect of the reverse reaction will not be very great and we can approximately calculate the quantum efficiency. Thus taking the results in Tables V and VII where the intensity of incident radiation (488.5 $\mu\mu$) was six Hefners-at-100 cm.,

Number of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per second

$$= 6 \times 900 \times \left(\frac{488 \times 10^{-7}}{3 \times 10^{10}} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{3.5 \times 10^{-21}} \right)$$

$$= 18.5 \times 10^{14} \text{ quanta per sq. cm. per second.}$$

(i) Taking the results in Table V where the change is 1.1 c.c.

N/500 Br per c.c. in the first twenty minutes we have

Number of gm. mols transformed per sq. cm. per second \times depth of reaction vessel (1.5 cm.)

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1.1}{1000 \times 1000} \times \frac{1}{20 \times 60} \times 1.5 \text{ gm. mols per sec.} \\ & = 18.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ gm. mols per sec.} \\ & = 18.8 \times 10^{-10} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23} \text{ mols per sec.} \\ & = 8.42 \times 10^{14} \text{ mols per sq. cm. per sec.} \end{aligned}$$

Thus about 1.5 quanta are necessary for one molecule transformed.

(ii) Taking the results in Table VII where the change is 0.7 c.c. N/500 Br per c.c. in the first 25 minutes we have

Number of gm. mols transformed per sq. cm. per sec.

$$\begin{aligned} & \times \text{depth of reaction vessel (1.5 cm.)} \\ & = \frac{.7}{1000 \times 1000} \times \frac{1}{25 \times 60} \times 1.5 \text{ gm. mols per sec.} \\ & = 7 \times 10^{-10} \text{ gm. mols per sec.} \\ & = 7 \times 10^{-10} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23} \\ & = 4.27 \times 10^{14} \text{ molecules per sq. cm. per sec.} \end{aligned}$$

Thus about 3 quanta are necessary for each molecule transformed. It is quite evident that the quantum efficiency is less than unity.

Probable Mechanism of the Photochemical Reaction between Bromine and m-Nitro-benzylidene Malonic Ester.

Any mechanism of reaction that may be proposed should be in a position to explain quantitatively the following facts:—

(a) That both the bromination and the reverse reaction are photo-chemical in nature.

(b) That the equilibrium constant $\frac{[\text{Dibromide}]}{[\text{Br}] \times [\text{Ester}]}$ is proportional

to the square root of the intensity of incident light.

(c) That the resultant velocity is given by the equation

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1 (a-x)^2 - k_2 x$$

(d) That the maximum transformation per quantum absorbed should be one molecule.

The investigations of Bodenstein and Berthoud lead to the general conclusion that the absorption of light by bromine results in the decomposition of the molecule of bromine into atoms. Recently Bernard Lewis in a note (*Nature*, April 2, 1927) has brought out evidence in favour of photochemical decomposition of hydrogen iodide into atoms of hydrogen and iodine, thus proving the untenability of the interpretation given by Stern and Volmar on the basis of excited molecules produced by the absorption of a quantum of light. We shall assume that the bromine atoms are the active agents in this photochemical reaction. Bonhoeffer (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 116, 391; 1926, 119, 385) finds that atomic hydrogen represents a metastable condition, whose life is of the order of 0.3 sec. under favourable conditions. This relatively long life is explained by assuming that two atoms cannot spontaneously recombine to form a molecule. In order that they may combine and lose the energy of recombination some third body must be present to take up this energy. This hypothesis of Bonhoeffer may be extended to the process of photobromination in solution. The concentration of bromine atoms at a steady state in solution will be determined by its rate of formation due to light absorbed by bromine molecules and the rate of recombination of bromine atoms in presence of a third body—mostly molecules of solvent under favourable conditions.

$$\frac{d[\text{Br}]}{dt} = k_1 I \text{ (absorbed)} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$- \frac{d[\text{Br}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Br}] [\text{Br}] [S] \text{ where } S \text{ is the con. of solvent}$$

molecules.

Since S is constant, at the steady state

$$[\text{Br}] = \sqrt{\frac{k_1 I}{k_2 S}} = k \sqrt{I} \quad \dots (2)$$

Some of the bromine atoms may, however, combine in a three body collision where the third body may be the ester molecule or the bromine molecule. We now postulate tentatively the following mechanism for the reaction studied here :

The effect is the same as if the following reaction takes place

and hence the rate of formation of the ester-dibromide is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & k_2 [\text{Br}] [\text{Br}] [\text{A}] [\text{Br}_2] \\ &= k_2 \sqrt{I} \sqrt{I} [\text{A}] [\text{Br}_2] \\ &= k_2 I (a-x) (b-x) \quad \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

where *a* is the initial conc. of ester and *b* the initial conc. of bromine and *x* the concentration of dibromide.

The reverse reaction

can only take place when the dibromide molecule collides with an atom of bromine. The velocity of this photo-decomposition is therefore given by the equation

$$k_3 [\text{X}] [\text{Br}] = k_3 \sqrt{I} [\text{X}] \quad \dots (5)$$

The observed velocity of photo-bromination is the difference between these two velocities, and has the value

$$k_2 I (a-x) (b-x) - k_3 \sqrt{I} [\text{X}] \quad \dots (6)$$

At the steady state when the equilibrium is reached,

Equation (6)=0 and we have

$$\frac{X}{(a-x) (b-x)} = \frac{k_2 I}{k_3 \sqrt{I}} = \frac{k_2 \sqrt{I}}{k_3} \quad \dots (7)$$

The mechanism proposed above also indicates that for every quantum of light absorbed the number of dibromide molecules that can be produced according to equation (3) cannot exceed unity.

We have thus been able to explain the experimental observations on the basis of a mechanism which is at least not more complicated than what obtains in this field.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY, DAOGA.

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